

NON-GOVERNANCE OF NATIONAL SPORTS FEDERATIONS: A CASE OF SRI LANKA

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Abstract

This study examines the occurrence of Non-Governance in national sport federation in Sri Lanka. While much of the existing literature emphasizes good governance practices, there is a notable gap regarding the causes and consequences of Non-Governance within national sport federations. This research aims to address this gap and contribute to the field of sport governance. A qualitative research approach was employed, using the Fishbone Model as the theoretical framework to identify root causes of governance failures. Thematic analysis was utilized to categorize and interpret the collected data. Sixteen key personnel from selected national sport federations were purposively sampled for in-depth interviews. Due to ethical considerations, the names of the federations are not disclosed. The findings are limited in generalizability as the study covers only a subset of ten federations out of seventy-four in the country. The study reveals root causes that contribute to the persistence of Non-Governance within these federations. It further highlights how personal prestige and power dynamics among officials often take precedence over the advancement of national sport performance, thereby sustaining the cycle of governance failures. This research concludes that addressing Non-Governance requires acknowledging the complex and interrelated causes that maintain it. Future research opportunities abound in this area, particularly using diverse methodologies to deepen understanding and propose solutions.

Keywords: Non-Governance, National Sport Federations, Fishbone Model

Introduction

Researchers have paid extensive attention to the field of sports governance. International sports organizations/institutions as well as governments have made direct interventions in this regard.

Among the issues reflected in all these areas, various studies have been conducted on the importance and necessity of applying the principles of good governance (Chappelet & Mrkonjic, 2013; Geeraert, 2015; Bayle & Madella, 2002). In addition, aspects such as corruption, fraud, irregularities, match-fixing, doping, bribery, financial irregularities, match-fixing, inefficiency, unethical decisions, mismanagement, etc (Geeraert, 2015; Chappelet & Mrkonjic, 2013; Maennig, 2005; Forster, 2006; Jennings, 2011). in the sports sector have also been discussed at length. Furthermore, there has been extensive attention paid to the principles of good governance, good governance practices, good governance indicators, policies, basic principles of the Olympic philosophy, and good governance guidelines that help create good governance in sports. Also, research has focused to some extent on the challenges and diversity in this regard. The observational methods required to evaluate governance have been introduced.

Research has been found on the weaknesses of sports governance (Geeraert, 2015; Chappelet & Mrkonjic, 2013; Alm, 2013; Forster, 2006; Grix, 2010). There, research has been conducted on how and why governance failures occur. Suggestions have been made to improve them. However, there are several points that become clear in further research on this. The first point is that not enough research has been done on bad sports governance. Second, there is a lack of research using case studies in the research conducted on good sports governance and Non-Governance. Third, there are insufficient tools to investigate why bad sports governance occurs. Therefore, it is timely to focus research on these areas as well. Because despite internationally accepted recommendations and guidelines in the field, Non-Governance continues to occur in sports organizations.

It is important to conduct research in various areas for the advancement and development of any field. It is important to conduct research based on not only good and bad, but also a combination of these (Geeraert, 2016; Dowling, Leopkey, & Smith, 2018; Parent & Hoye, 2018). Through this, the subject develops, there is an opportunity to conduct in-depth studies, there is a space to formulate correct decisions and policies, and there is an ability to accurately identify the scope. Therefore, researchers conducting research on sports governance as well as policy makers working on sports governance are motivated to conduct studies in various directions.

Thus, despite the extensive studies, criteria and approaches regarding sports governance, it is explored **why does Non-Governance happens in national sports federations**. Accordingly,

it is also explored what factors have influenced the occurrence of Non-Governance. This will contribute to the nutrition of the research literature on Non-Governance and contribute to increasing the interest of researchers related to Non-Governance.

Theoretical Framework

Why does Non-Governance happen in the National Sports Federations (NSF)? This is a problem. Accordingly, the theoretical approach of the Fishbein model is used to find out what causes are affecting this. This is also known as the Ishikawa diagram or the cause-and-effect diagram. This diagram model was presented by Kamaru Ishikawa in the 1960s. The basis for it is formed as a result of an attempt to systematically identify the root causes of a specific problem. This model, which was created for industrial quality control, has later been used as a conceptual framework for studies in various fields. Through this, it is possible to identify causes, classify causes and identify other factors. Moreover, researchers are able to analyze the identified issues more clearly, accurately and logically. That is, there is the ability to activate systematic reasoning. This facilitates easier clustering in complex situations with multiple interrelated causes. Kumar and Sharma, 2018 have stated that this approach helps to observe the underlying roots of the phenomenon, not just by observing superficial facts.

This model can be used not only for qualitative research but also for quantitative and mixed methods research. Thematic coding, used in qualitative research, is a method of data analysis that uses thematic coding to meaningfully collect interview responses or observation data and use it as clusters (grouping/grouping) (Paton, 2015). It is an approach that can also be used to improve the logicity and meaningfulness of the data prepared in this way when analyzing it. This model has been used in management (Meadows, 2008; George et al., 2005; Singh and Sharma, 2021; Rahman et al., 2022; Grindil, 2007) and social science (World Bank, 2018; Islam and Sakamoto, 2021; Ndebele, 2017; Dhakru, 2020; Mukherjee, Patel, and Agarwal, 2020; Marmot et al., 2010) research. It can be used for participatory research as well as action research. Another advantage is that research can be conducted with predefined categories (different concepts, etc.) and the data can be adjusted accordingly. Sometimes themes emerge from the research data itself and can then be structured and presented as a cause-and-effect structure. Yin, 2018 has shown that the dual approaches and flexibility inherent in this approach make it useful for studies conducted through theoretical approaches as well as case studies. Creswell, 2018 has stated that this theoretical approach can also be used to effectively communicate the findings

of applied research to the reader.

The primary objective of this research, which follows a qualitative research approach, is to study the causes and effects that have influenced the occurrence of Non-Governance in NSF's and to examine the effects accordingly. When obtaining research data through the interview method, this theoretical approach can be considered a more accurate choice due to its ability to identify causes and effects and identify root causes. This theory will also help to conduct qualitative data analysis more effectively.

Governance Approaches of National Sport Federations in Sri Lanka (NSFsSL)

By 2025, National Sports Federations/Associations have been registered for 74 sports in Sri Lanka. All of these are primarily controlled under the Ministry of Sports and Youth Affairs. In addition, only National Sports Federations/Associations formed for Olympic sports are required to be registered under the National Olympic Committee of Sri Lanka. The main role of the National Sports Federations/Associations is to the development and governance of sports within a country.

And also, growth and management of sports in a nation. They oversee national teams, carry out development projects, and assist local clubs and competitions etc. Additionally, NSF's guarantee integrity, fair play, and the general well-being of their respective sports. The registration and dissolution of national sports associations in Sri Lanka are outlined in Sections 28 to 35 of Part III of the Sports Act, No. 25 of 1973 (Sport Act, 1973) in Sri Lanka. These federations/associations primary goals are to: develop sports in the nation; regulate sports; affiliate district federations and sports clubs; adopt and implement sport-related rules and regulations; prepare plans for the development of sports in the nation; host national and international competitions; oversee and manage sports competitions held in the nation; choose athletes and officials to represent the nation in international competitions; and train coaches, referees, judges, and other personnel. As a result, it is evident that the National Sports Federation (NSFs) is a body that has obtained legal authority over the relevant sport. However, adherence to the laws, rules, and regulations of the relevant international organization as well as the relevant country's government is crucial when establishing a NSF's. The Sports Act contains information on how to register a National Federation of Sri Lanka, as well as the necessary steps and suspensions.

The study was carried out in a selected NSF's that was in charge of managing a significant team sport in Sri Lanka. Despite being active domestically and abroad, the federation has not yet

earned a spot at the Olympic Games. It is affiliated with national and international governing bodies and operates as a non-profit organization per Sri Lankan sports law (Sports Act No. 25 of 1973 and its amendments). Although the federation oversees men's and women's national teams, most leadership positions are held by men. The federation's governance structure includes a president, secretary, treasurer, and executive committee members. Annual general assemblies and executive meetings are the main venues for governance decisions.

Methodology

This study employed a Qualitative Research Approach (QRA) to gain an in-depth understanding of persistent issues in sport governance. The QRA, combining interviews, document analysis, and model-based data presentation, allowed for a robust exploration of governance issues, providing rich evidence for practical recommendations and future research. Qualitative methods are particularly suited to exploring complex social phenomena, allowing researchers to capture the nuanced perspectives of individuals involved in sport organizations (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This study is based on secondary data. It can be divided into three main themes such as critical literature reviewed, systematically reviewed and documentary method. Data was collected through multiple sources to ensure methodological triangulation, enhancing the validity and reliability of findings (Denzin, 2018). The primary data collection method involved semi-structured interviews with 16 key actors purposively selected for their extensive experience in NSF's. Data collection focused on two core questions designed to uncover both the causes and consequences of Non-Governance: (1) Why does Non-Governance continuously occur in NSF's? and (2) What are the outcomes of such governance failures? These targeted questions allowed for a focused yet rich discussion relevant to the research objectives. Interviews were conducted remotely through Zoom and telephone conversations due to logistical constraints and to ensure participant convenience. All sessions were audio-recorded with consent, enabling accurate transcription and analysis (Opdenakker, 2006; Nowell et al., 2021). Purposive sampling is widely recognized in qualitative research to target participants who have rich, relevant knowledge about the phenomenon under study (Palinkas et al., 2015). The participants had all worked in various leadership and administrative roles within NSF's for more than ten years, providing informed insights into governance challenges. While the majority were men, this demographic characteristic reflects the gender composition of governance positions within many sports organizations globally (Fink, 2016). Notably, all participants were no longer actively involved in the federations at the time of the

study, which facilitated candid reflections on governance issues without current political pressures.

For data analysis, the study applied the Fishbone model, a theoretical framework often used to analyze attitudes and behaviors in organizational studies (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010). This model was adapted to map the factors influencing governance practices and the outcomes of Non-Governance within NSFs. Data was systematically coded and presented through Fishbein diagrams, which visually represent the relationships among beliefs, attitudes, and behavioral intentions related to governance. The visual representation facilitated clearer interpretation and communication of complex qualitative findings (Miles, Huberman, & Saldana, 2019). In addition to interviews, secondary data sources were systematically reviewed, including official websites of sport federations, relevant media articles, and newspapers. This documentary analysis provided complementary contextual information and helped triangulate findings from the interviews (Bowen, 2009). The use of multiple data sources is a recommended practice in qualitative sport governance research to build a comprehensive understanding of governance dynamics (Hoye et al., 2015). Furthermore, to contextualize the findings and highlight broader implications "Thematic analysis", which is popular as a qualitative research reasoning method, has been used for this purpose. Scholars who have presented arguments in this regard have pointed out that this is a method that can be used to identify, analyze, organize, describe, and report on themes found in a set of data found through research (Boyatzis, 1998; Ryan & Bernard, 2000; Holloway & Todres, 2003; Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Results and Discussion

This research has focused on why Non-Governance continuously happens withing NSFs. Based on the qualitative research approach this study found that amount of information by looking at the major two questions that researcher inquired. The first question is (1) Why does Non-Governance continuously occur in NSFs. The second research question is (2) What are the outcomes of such governance failures? To answer those questions researchers used Fishbone Model as major theoretical framework. Go through it this section aligned under few themes such as demographic information about key actors of the NSF's, Non-Governance of NSFs, connecting around Non-Governance of NSF's, outcomes of the governance failures in NSFs. All these themes originated through the following data sources such as literature review, document review, website observation and interviews.

Influence of Participant Demographics on Non-Governance Perspectives

This research purposely used to gather data through the key actors of the NSFs in Sri Lanka who actively participated in the federations work. These key actors were found the word of mouth during the special gathering at the sport related workshops in the year 2024. Table 01 shows that the demographic information of interviewees.

Table 1. Demographic information of interviewees

Participant ID (Ex: P1)	Age Range	Sport Background	Role/Position in NSFs (Former)	Gender	Years of Experience	Current Occupation	Educational Qualifications (Sport)
P1	40-49	Team Sport	Former Vice President	Male	5+	Self-employer	No
P2	50-59	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Self-employer	Yes
P3	60-69	Team Sport	Former committee member	Male	5+	Freelancer	No
P4	40-49	Team Sport	Former Treasurer	Male	5+	Self-employer	No
P5	40-49	Team Sport	Former committee member	Male	5+	Entrepreneur	No
P6	40-49	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Business Owner	No
P7	50-59	Team Sport	Former Vice President	Male	5+	Retired	No
P8	50-59	Team Sport	Former Vice President	Female	5+	Consultant	Yes
P9	40-49	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Freelancer	No
P10	50-59	Team Sport	Former committee member	Male	5+	Retired	No
P11	50-59	Team Sport	Former committee member	Male	5+	Entrepreneur	No
P12	40-49	Team Sport	Former committee member	Male	5+	Private Sector	No
P13	50-59	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Business Owner	No
P14	40-49	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Entrepreneur	No
P15	40-49	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Private Sector	Yes
P16	50-59	Team Sport	Former EXCO member	Male	5+	Self-employer	Yes

Source: Author’s own contribution

Fifteen male and one female from the NSFs were participated in this study. Key roles held by participants included Vice President (3), Treasurer (1), executive committee members (7), and committee members (5). They were between the ages of 40 and 59. Most participants (16 out of 16) had at least a bachelor's degree, especially in management rather than sport, and had

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more than five years of experience in NSF's governance and administration. Few had a sports diploma, which includes courses in coaching and administration. These demographic characteristics had an impact on participants' perceptions and applications of accountability and transparency. Long-serving participants, for example, frequently brought up informal governance procedures and institutional memory.

"We don't always need written records," said participant 2

A male executive committee member with six years of experience.

"We've been here long enough to understand how things operate here" said participant 9.

These opinions suggested a possible disconnect between long-standing customs and contemporary governance norms since they emphasized tradition over official documentation. Another important factor was educational background. International governance principles were more clearly aligned with those who had earned a sport diploma. The following was said by participant 8, a female former vice president who holds a master's degree in management:

"Transparency entails keeping records, releasing reports, and informing the public of developments." Otherwise, people will stop trusting NSF's".

Those with technical degrees or real-world experience, on the other hand, tended to use more relational definitions of good and Non-Governance, like loyalty and internal trust.

Perceptions of conflict of interest and ethical norms were also impacted by gender. Concerns regarding the fairness and transparency of decision-making were more prevalent among female participants. A female former vice president who served for five years, participant 8, shared:

"A lot of decisions are made without candid discussion. Sometimes we don't know until everything is decided".

This brought attention to alleged disparities in power and a deficiency in inclusive governance procedures. Senior participants also expressed more negative opinions about the lack of regular evaluation procedures. 54-year-old male participant 16, a former member of the EXCO, observed:

"We lack a suitable framework for assessing our own choices. It appears we simply continue without stopping to think".

These results imply that people's expectations and perceptions of NSF's governance in Sri Lanka are influenced by demographic traits like age, gender, experience, and education. Comprehending these factors is crucial for customizing inclusive and contextually appropriate governance reforms.

It was revealed that women have been given less space in the context of decision-making in NSFs in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, this reveals that the decisions of NSFs are framed in a way that is suitable for men. Furthermore, although it is clear that educational qualifications are an essential factor for administration, the importance of understanding the subject matter related to each field is reflected in this. It was revealed that despite serving on a voluntary basis in a national sports federation for more than 5 years, no NSFs has taken any action to seek their services or advice again. This was revealed by investigating information about their current employment. It was revealed through interviews that none of these 16 have contributed to any work of the NSFs since leaving those positions. However, they were willing to contribute whenever necessary on behalf of the NSFs or for the sake of Sri Lankan sports. Accordingly, it is confirmed that there is no mechanism for obtaining services or advice from retirees within the NSFs and that the needs for this have not been identified.

Fishbone Model Applied to Non-Governance of NSFs of Sri Lanka

The Fishbone Model was used to identify the reasons behind the Non-Governance within NSFs. All the discussions obtained through the interviews were transcribed. For this, information was obtained for each key actor (16) within a maximum period of 30 to 40 minutes. All the discussions were conducted in the mother language (Sinhala). During transcription, they were translated into English. The summary information list prepared based on the 16 interview transcripts is shown in figure 1. Using this figure, efforts were made to identify mal governance practices through the Fishbone model. Here, attention was paid to research question (1) why does Non-Governance continuously occur in NSF's?

The Fishbone model, which explains the factors that contribute to the persistence of Non-Governance in many national sports federations in Sri Lanka, reveals the lack of understanding in this regard, according to the facts stated by experienced officials in this regard.

“Wrongful actions are not done in NSFs without knowing it. They make these bad decisions with good understanding. Because there is no mechanism to monitor these. Therefore, when one person does these things, they become a tradition. The damage is increasing day by day”.

Another participant 7 said,

“Wrong decisions were made during our time. Even though we tried to correct them, those in power were not willing to comply with them. Even today, we see those actions in our federations. Even after years, they have not changed”.

Another participant 12 said,

“It is thus clear that the wrong practices of working in the same position for a long time have made it difficult to implement correct governance”. Another participant 4 said, “Sometimes there was a mentality back then that others depended on the person who had been in the same position for a long time. He understands. So, we will implement that decision”. These are the situations that exist in the federations. “The constitutions are not remembered. When our people work and make decisions, they are just a document”. They added.

This clearly shows the underestimation of the basic issues of transparency, accountability, integrity and ethical considerations, which are an essential part of proper governance. Scholars explained that key factors of good governance include such as transparency, accountability, democracy, and internal integrity (Rassouli et al., 2020; Budevici-Puiu et al., 2020). It will not only affect the governance of the game but also enhance the skills of the game.

The need for constant monitoring by responsible parties and updating legal policies also emerged through this. According to the Fishbein model (figure 1), the most accurate understanding is that the persistence of Non-Governance in NSF’s is due to the behavior of responsible officials, entrenched in normative beliefs, political interference, tolerance for unethical practices, personal interests, weak control, creating an environment that fosters normative attitudes, the emergence of a culture of conformity, and discourages reform.

“When you question something, you are considered a troublemaker.” Participant 4 said,

Figure 1: Fishbone Model Applied to Non-Governance in NSF’s in Sri Lanka

Source: Author’s own contribution

This confirms that there is no interest in correcting Non-Governance. This then hinders their agendas. This also confirms the awareness of good governance and the way in which Non-Governance has become part of the NSF's management process itself. This interviews data also helped to understand how NSFs are using the sport and their positions for their own benefit, not for the good of the sport.

Connecting around Non-Governance of NSF's

It is possible to understand more precisely why Non-Governance occurs in national sports federations. There are several reasons that are implied in this. The first of these is that Non-Governance is not based on one reason or one person. The second is that Non-Governance does not occur based on single failures alone, and the third is that Non-Governance consistently occurs in national federations based on a combination of root causes, such as individual intentions, institutional weaknesses, administrative weaknesses, leadership weaknesses, structural weaknesses, cultural acceptance and external forces. Each of these root causes reinforces each other, indicating the use of corrupt governance to maintain the status quo. This is illustrated in the summary table 2 prepared by the analysis of the underlying data.

Table 2: Root Causes for Non-Governance of NSFs

Core Cause	Specific Factors Feeding the Cause
1. Personal Gain	2. Self-interest - Corruption - Financial misappropriation
3. Power Dynamics	4. Authority misuse - Lack of accountability
5. Weak Organizational Systems	6. Lack of transparency - Inadequate checks & balances
7. Lack of Monitoring	8. Weak regulatory bodies - Infrequent audits - No sanctions for misconduct
9. Cultural and Social Norms	10. Normalization of unethical practices - Nepotism - Loyalty over merit
11. External Pressures	12. Political interference - Pressure from sponsors/stakeholders - Media influence
13. Fear of Change	14. Resistance to reforms - Fear of losing power or position

Source: Author's own contribution

The Persistence of Non-Governance Practices and Their effects on Sri Lanka's NSFs

The growth and integrity of Sri Lanka's sporting ecosystem have been severely hampered by the ongoing existence of Non-Governance practices within NSFs. These governance shortcomings, which have their roots in a complicated web of systemic, cultural, and individual-level shortcomings, have had far-reaching effects on performance outcomes as well

as structure. The pursuit of personal gain, where officials put their own interests, corruption, and financial misappropriation ahead of the general welfare, is one of the main causes.

This way of thinking has created a culture of conflict of interest, where choices are made not to further the objectives of the sport but to benefit people or organizations that support those in positions of authority. Resource misallocation, a decline in public confidence, and a structural inability to put athletes' well-being and athletic prowess first are the outcomes. The power dynamics that are ingrained in these organizations are another significant factor. A small number of people or groups have been able to control decision-making processes due to abuses of authority, a lack of accountability, and the concentration of power. This concentration of power suppresses different points of view, threatens democratic systems of government, and deters internal dissension or change.

Mismanagement becomes commonplace when oversight is resisted, and checks are disregarded. Stakeholder voices are marginalized, transparency is decreased, and institutional legitimacy is eroded because of these dynamics. As a result, many federations find it difficult to carry out long-term strategic plans, frequently alternating between policies that are driven more by personal agendas or shifting political allegiances than by needs assessments supported by evidence.

A third cause is the incompetence of officials and leaders, which frequently results from a lack of governance training, inexperience, and poor leadership abilities. People who gain leadership roles through connections or favoritism rather than hard work frequently lack the technical know-how and strategic acumen required to run a sports organization in a cutthroat international environment. This results in frequent administrative errors, missed development opportunities, and ineffective decision-making. For example, poor leadership can be linked to mishandled athlete development programs, delayed national competition planning, and noncompliance with international standards.

As a result of procedural or governance-related infractions, Sri Lanka's NSFs frequently suffer from international shame, penalties, or disqualification. Weak organizational structures exacerbate the issue on a structural level. Many federations function without robust internal controls, meaningful performance reviews, or sufficient transparency procedures. Because of this organizational weakness, decisions are made without adequate documentation, financial transactions are not adequately documented, and roles and responsibilities are not clearly defined. Any hope for institutional reform is dashed and public oversight is weakened in the

absence of accountability mechanisms. Because of this, these federations frequently struggle to draw in top-notch athletes, sponsors, or foreign collaborations, all of which are essential for infrastructure development and athlete support. Another important cause is the social and cultural norms that govern sport in India. Unethical practices like nepotism and favoritism, in which friends, family, or political allies are appointed to important positions regardless of their qualifications, are frequently normalized. Competent people are deterred from using the system by this loyalty-over-merit culture, which feeds a vicious cycle of stagnation and poor performance. The ingrained notion that “this is how it's always been done” strengthens opposition to change. Younger professionals and outside experts are consequently frequently marginalized, which restricts the introduction of fresh concepts and advancements into sports management. This cultural inertia deters modernization efforts that are necessary for maintaining global competitiveness and guarantees the continuation of antiquated policies.

Political meddling, which has long afflicted Sri Lanka's NSFs, is another potent external cause. Sport organizations are frequently used by political actors as platforms for patronage, visibility, or influence. Institutional autonomy is distorted by this meddling, which compels federations to put political objectives ahead of moral leadership or athletic achievement. For instance, the technical integrity of sports planning is jeopardized by politically driven funding choices or leadership appointments. Furthermore, rather than bringing about significant structural changes, pressure from sponsors, stakeholders, or the media frequently leads to token reforms meant to appease the public. Despite being external, these pressures gain traction within federations because of their lack of autonomous governance mechanisms and poor internal resilience.

Reform initiatives are also hampered by long-standing administrators' fear of change. Many people oppose governance reform because they worry about losing their resources, influence, or visibility. This institutional inertia leads to stagnation, where ineffective systems, out-of-date laws, and policies are maintained in spite of their glaring shortcomings. Sri Lanka's sport federations frequently lag behind their international counterparts due to their unwillingness to adopt contemporary governance models or adhere to international standards. This in turn affects long-term sporting success, particularly in Olympic and international arenas, as well as athlete preparation and talent identification.

The absence of reliable monitoring systems is closely related. In many federations, internal auditing systems and regulatory bodies are either non-existent or very weak. There is little

deterrence against unethical behavior because audits are infrequent, there are no sanctions for misconduct, and the rules are not strictly enforced. Even when governance violations do occur, they are either disregarded or not sufficiently addressed because there are no independent watchdogs or compliance officers. This impunity encourages wrongdoers and sends a message to others that bad leadership is acceptable, if not encouraged. As a result, unethical behavior, financial theft, and discrimination in athlete selection procedures continue unchecked, seriously harming Sri Lankan sport organizations' reputations.

A systemic breakdown of legitimacy, performance, and trust in Sri Lankan sports is the result of these governance failures taken together. National federations frequently run afoul of international governing bodies because they fail to uphold the fundamental values of inclusivity, autonomy, and transparency. Due to inconsistent support, subpar training facilities, and political manipulation during the selection process, athletes who ought to be the main beneficiaries of these organizations suffer. The pipeline for sport development is still broken, with promising talent being lost because of administrative neglect, poor management, or a lack of support. Furthermore, due to financial ambiguity and reputational harm, international funding and sponsorship opportunities are frequently lost.

In conclusion, a series of detrimental effects have resulted from the persistence of Non-Governance in Sri Lanka's NSFs. These causes, which have their roots in power struggles, personal motivations, structural inefficiencies, cultural complacency, and outside manipulations, have resulted in a variety of outcomes, from poor financial management to a halt in the advancement of athletics. Sri Lanka's potential as a competitive sporting nation on the international scene will be undermined if these causes are not addressed through robust reforms, open leadership, institutional accountability, and a change in governance culture. The foundation of national sporting pride, organizational sustainability, and athletic success is governance reform, which is more than just a bureaucratic endeavor.

Conclusion

Deeply detrimental repercussions have resulted from the ongoing use of Non-Governance practices in NSFsSL. These causes such as personal benefit, concentrated power, incapacity, cultural inertia, shoddy systems, and political meddling have all worked together to erode the effectiveness, openness, and integrity of the nation's athletic institutions. Every governance failure, as shown by the fishbone analysis(Figure 2), has resulted in observable setbacks, from poor international representation and a decline in public trust to resource mismanagement and

athlete neglect. NSFSSL. NSFs run the risk of continuing to deteriorate in the absence of immediate, systemic changes, such as capable leadership, open systems, independent supervision, and a change in the culture of governance. In addition to being crucial for enhancing credibility and performance, addressing these underlying issues is also necessary to fully realize Sri Lanka's potential as a major international athletic power.

Figure 2: Fishbone Model Applied to Resulting Effects

Source: Author's own contribution

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